

MICRO PLASTICS

HORIZON 2020
PAPILLONS

Plastic in Agricultural Production:
Impacts, Lifecycles and LONG-term Sustainability

THE MAGAZINE - Stakeholder forum, special edition - April 2025

THE SCALE OF THE CHALLENGE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000210

<https://www.papillons-h2020.eu/>

papillons@farm-europe.eu

TABLE OF

EDITORIAL PAGE 4

LATEST SCIENCE NEWS PAGE 6

**LIFE OF THE
CONSORTIUM** PAGE 10

INTERVIEWS

D. Briassoulis PAGE 12

R. Hurley PAGE 14

S. Selonen PAGE 18

V. Sannakajsa PAGE 20

**PLASTICS IN
VINEYARDS** PAGE 22

**PAPILLON'S CALL FOR
ACTION** PAGE 24

**PAPILLON'S MESSAGE
TO POLICY MAKERS** PAGE 28

**SEE YOU SOON,
PAPILLONS!** PAGE 30

CONTENTS

A wooden crate filled with fresh vegetables including tomatoes, eggplants, carrots, and peppers, set against a background of a vegetable garden.

Authors: Luca Nizetto, Demetres Briassoulis, Rachel Hurley, Salla Selonen,
Velmala Sannakajsa, Valentina Tartiu, Luc Vernet, Alessandra Diana,
Micol Cattana, Noelia Cano Santamaría, Lionel Changeur.
papillons@farm-europe.eu
Rond Point Schuman, 9
1040 Brussels BELGIUM
Copyright © 2025 Consortium PAPILLIONS.

Editorial

Welcome to the final event of the PAPHILLONS' research project supported by the Horizon 2020 programme! As Work Package leader for communication and dissemination, Farm Europe is delighted to present this special edition. We want to take this opportunity to warmly thank the research partners that have contributed to this project which shed lights on one of the main threat for agricultural soils: micro & nano plastics. And also to thank all of you, scientists, policy makers, farmers, industry or NGO representatives that have been accompanying us until today.

As Farm Europe, we know particularly well that soils are the main asset for our farmers, they are a common heritage to grow our food today, and for the next generations, to contribute to the climate challenge enhancing their capacity to store carbone, and also to further increase their productivity to contribute to the boom of bioeconomy while protecting biodiversity. We need soils in good health!

That's why we are particularly concerned by the alerts we received publication after publication on the results delivered by the consortium.

In these columns, you will discover that the dissemination of micro & nano plastics is going far beyond our initial expectations. In the European Union, we are almsot at the same levels as China where research on this topic is more advanced. You will read evidences highlighted by our researchers on the fact that our soils are on the verge of being structurally transformed by these contaminants with possible impacts on productivity in sight. You will also see that solutions are not straightforward.

The agricultural plastics community is and need to be mobilised to overcome this challenge, fighting against mis-management and promoting best practices. But this won't be enough because a wide share of the highly volatile micro & nano plastics pollution does not come from the farms, but from our society more broadly: urban composts, industrial emissions, etc. A wide mobilisation is needed, in addition to further research and innovation.

At a time when the European Union is finalising the soil monitoring law and preparing a new bioeconomy strategy, the outcome of PAPHILLONS is a chance to build a robust and science-based policy framework to further develop our EU agriculture and protect our soils.

Luc Vernet, Editor
Secretary General of Farm Europe

Partnerships

FRONTIER LABORATORIES LTD

Frontier Laboratories Ltd., founded 1991, is a global leading company in analytical pyrolysis, based in Japan. Frontier Lab is consistently doing research and development of analytical pyrolysis instruments and methods, and manufacturing pyrolyzers with associated accessories for a wide range of analytical applications that include physical property evaluation of polymer materials used in various advanced scientific fields such as quality control in aircraft and automobile industries, differentiation of rubber, paint, paper in forensic investigations, and identification of environmental pollutants such as microplastics. Frontier Lab's analytical pyrolyzer (EGA/PY-3030D) and accessories can be easily installed on almost all commercially available GC/MS systems. FLAB's distribution partners are supported by Frontier Lab's regional product specialists and business development managers. In Europe, Dr. Michael Soll, located in Germany, is representing Frontier Laboratories since more than 10 years.

microplastics

an Open Access Journal by MDPI

MICROPLASTICS

Microplastics is an international, peer-reviewed, open access journal on the science and technology of primary and secondary microplastics published quarterly online by MDPI. The journal is indexed within ESCI (Web of Science), Scopus, EBSCO, and other databases. The aim of *Microplastics* is to publish papers in the field of microplastic sources, sinks and environmental fate, their potential effect on ecosystem services and human life, and mitigation measures to reduce the adverse effects of microplastics. The journal has no restrictions regarding the length of papers. Full experimental details should be provided so that the results can be reproduced.

LATEST SCIENCE NEWS

The Impact of Nanoplastics on Groundwater and Soil Health

By Rieckhof C., Martínez-Hernández V., Holzbecher E, Meffe R.

The presence of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) in the environment has raised increasing concern about their potential impact on ecosystems and environmental health, prompting further research on their effects. This study by Fundacion IMDEA Agua on polystyrene micro- and nanoplastics sheds light on how these particles move through quartz sand under unsaturated conditions (i.e. a state where the soil or porous material contains both water and air, but the pore spaces are not completely filled with water), revealing potential risks for soil health and groundwater contamination.

Researchers found that smaller MNPs, approximately 120 nm in size, can easily pass through sand, with around 95% recovery. This high mobility suggests that these particles have the potential to reach groundwater. On the other hand, medium-sized particles, ranging between 500 and 1000 nm, exhibit a phenomenon known as "size exclusion." They tend to travel rapidly through larger pathways while bypassing tighter spaces within the sand structure.

In contrast, larger particles, measuring approximately 10,000 nm, become trapped in the sand and are unable to move through small soil pores. This process, referred to as "straining," prevents them from infiltrating deeper layers of soil.

The study also highlighted the role of

physical and chemical interactions in MNP movement. Both particle size and the structure of the sand significantly influence how MNPs travel. While modeling reveals that larger MNPs remain stable in suspension, they are less likely to penetrate deeper soil layers due to physical retention mechanisms.

These findings carry important environmental implications. The ability of smaller MNPs to travel freely through soil presents a risk of groundwater contamination. As these particles move downward, they may carry harmful pollutants into deeper soil layers, potentially affecting groundwater sources that serve as vital drinking water supplies. Another significant concern is the so-called "Trojan Horse" effect, where mobile MNPs act as carriers for other toxic chemicals. This raises further questions about the types of contaminants that may be transported into sensitive ecosystems alongside these plastic particles.

Additionally, the accumulation of larger, retained MNPs in soil could disrupt water retention and nutrient cycling processes and could even enter the food chain through soil organisms.

Given these potential risks, the study underscores the need for continued research on MNP behavior in natural soils. As plastic pollution continues to increase, understanding how these particles move through the environment is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate their impact on ecosystems and human health.

Nanoplastics Travelling Across the Food Chain: Effects on Lettuce and Snails

By Zantis L., M. Kazour, Borchì C., Agati R., Colpaert R., Gimbert F., Vijver M., Peijnenburg W., Bosker T.

The study explores how nanoplastics (NPs) move through a terrestrial food chain, specifically from lettuce to snails, and assesses the potential impacts on both organisms. Using europium-doped polystyrene nanoplastics (Eu-PS), researchers uncovered some fascinating insights on the uptake and movement of these particles.

The researchers highlighted that nanoplastics were absorbed mainly by the plants' roots, with smaller amounts reaching the leaves. Interestingly, while lettuce growth was not severely impacted, the root dry weight increased at higher NPs concentrations.

On their side, the snails ingested NPs through contaminated lettuce (on which they were fed), but no detectable levels of particles were found in their digestive glands. Instead, NPs were found in their feces, showing that while ingestion occurred, absorption was limited. Although the snails' overall growth (biomass) was not affected, the study observed a decrease in shell diameter in snails after the ingestion of NPs, indicating some physiological effects.

In conclusion, nanoplastics can transfer through the food chain, but their ability to enter tissues appears limited under tested conditions. However, the potential for NPs to move up the food chain, potentially affecting humans, raises important questions for food safety and environmental health.

A GIS-based Methodology to Better Manage the Agricultural Plastic Waste Flow

By Convertino F., Vox G., Blanco I., Hachem A., Schettini E.

Plastic is widely used in agriculture and constitutes a viable means to increase the sector's productivity. But what happens when these materials reach the end of their life cycle? The mismanagement of agricultural plastic waste (APW) leads to pollution, soil contamination, and inefficiencies in waste disposal. A new study by the Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro proposes an innovative approach to tackle this challenge by establishing a scientific methodology to improve the design of the collection and transport system of APW, providing empirical evidence supporting its benefits. PAPPILLONS researchers developed a GIS-based methodology (Geographic Information System) to optimize the management of plastic waste from farms. The province of Bari was selected as a case study, a region generating a significant amount of APW.

Key findings show that the design of an effective system for managing plastic waste flow can increase recycling opportunities and sustainability. For instance, the introduction of intermediate collection centres significantly improves efficiency. This system reduces waste transport distances by 62% and lowers CO₂ emissions by 20% compared to direct farm-to-recycling transport.

Additionally, the study mapped out the best locations for these collection centres, considering environmental, social, and economic factors. This approach helps farmers manage waste more efficiently, reduces transportation costs and emissions, and boosts recycling opportunities. With better planning and investment in waste collection infrastructure, agriculture can become greener and more circular.

Biodegradable Microplastics' Influence on Lettuce

By Adamczyk S., Zantis L., Van Loon S., Van Gestel C.A.M., Bosker T., Hurley R., Nizzetto L., Adamczyk B., Velmala S.

PBAT biodegradable microplastics have an impact on plant growth and defence mechanisms, according to PAPILLONS study. Conducted with lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) in controlled conditions, the research highlights the environmental influence of biodegradable plastics in soils.

The experiment showed that higher concentrations of biodegradable microplastics negatively impacted lettuce growth. Plants exposed to elevated levels of these particles exhibited reduced shoot height, fewer leaves, and lower nitrogen levels in their foliage. Although overall growth was not significantly stunted, the presence of 0.8% biodegradable microplastics led to noticeable deterioration in specific growth traits.

Biochemical analyses revealed that lettuce exposed to biodegradable microplastics experienced oxidative stress. This was evident from increased lipid peroxidation, a known marker of cell damage. In response, the plants activated their defence mechanisms by producing higher levels of antioxidants and stress-related compounds, such as salicylic acid, to counteract the damage. Additionally, chlorophyll content decreased, suggesting a potential impairment of photosynthesis under prolonged or high-concentration exposure.

The study also examined plant resilience to biodegradable microplastics. At lower concentrations, lettuce plants were able to manage moderate stress by activating their natural defence pathways. However, when exposed to higher levels, their ability to maintain oxidative balance weakened, leading to a decline in resilience.

These findings suggest that biodegradable plastics, despite their environmentally friendly purpose, can accumulate in soil and subtly alter plant growth and health. To fully understand the long-term implications of these materials on agricultural soils, further research is needed under real-world conditions and across a wider range of crop species.

TAKE THE SURVEY AND SHAPE THE FUTURE OF PLASTIC USE IN EUROPEAN AGRICULTURE

Are you a Farmer and you are interested in the issue of Plastic Pollution in your soils?

PAPILLONS, funded by the European Commission, invites farmers to take part in an important survey on plastic use in European agriculture as part of the Papillons project,

The survey aims to:

- ✓ Identify the different plastic products used in crop production
- ✓ Assess the quantity of plastic utilized in agriculture across Europe

The collected data will contribute to a comprehensive map of plastic use in agriculture, supporting farmers, advisors, and policymakers in developing more sustainable practices. It will also aid companies and researchers in creating environmentally friendly materials and improving waste management systems.

How can you help and participate?
Scan the following QR CODE!

 20 minutes (estimated)

 Note: Before starting, you should refer to the provided catalogue for reference when answering

During AFP2025 a dedicated stand will be set up in Room NL1+2. Do not hesitate to share your doubts and questions with us!

Your input is **valuable** in shaping the future of sustainable agriculture in Europe. Let's work together for a greener future!

Life of the Consortium

Workshops with Finnish and Irish Farmers

Between October 2024 and March 2025, the Papillons consortium under Work Package 4 has been mobilising to assess the socio-economic sustainability of agricultural plastics (AP), bridging critical gaps in our understanding of AP impacts on farm economics, social, and environmental costs. This knowledge is essential for informed decisions at both the farm and policy levels.

In this context, Papillons partners from The Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA), Natural Resources Institute Finland (LUKE), and Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) hosted several stakeholder workshops, both online and in-person - in Finland and Ireland- using these two countries as case studies to explore the socio-economic impact of APs. The workshops offered a rich exchange of insights with the farming community, enabling us to consolidate existing knowledge and gather valuable data for our sustainability analysis.

Technical days organised by the CPA-INRAE in Bordeaux

Representatives of PAPHILLONS from NIVA and Farm Europe took part in the Journée Technique CPA-INRAE on March 20, 2025. This event brought together researchers, industry representatives, and stakeholders to discuss the impact of plastics in agriculture and the environment. Activities included workshops, round tables, and networking sessions. Key issues addressed included soil contamination by microplastics, sustainable plastic management, and biodegradable solutions for the agricultural sector.

The consortium members actively contributed to the discussions: Luc Vernet (Farm Europe) moderated a roundtable on the Sampling and analysis of microplastics highlighting the importance of establishing a science-based framework for sampling protocols to monitor microplastics in soils at the European level, in the context of the upcoming Soil Monitoring Directive.

Rachel Hurley (NIVA) presented PAPHILLONS' role in bridging knowledge gaps through coordinated spatial sampling and the development of a harmonized methodology. Luca Nizzetto (NIVA), on his side, emphasized that microplastic pollution is a present threat, with significant implications for soil and human health, plant growth, and ecosystem balance. He also participated as a panellist in a roundtable on biodegradable mulch films, where he underscored the need for a science-based regulatory framework on the management of biodegradable agricultural plastics and a thorough ecotoxicological risk assessment to consider long-term risks for soil health.

Upcoming round of negotiations on a Global Plastics Treaty

PAPHILLONS has been following closely international negotiations at the United Nations (UN) around a legally binding instrument to fight against plastic pollution and its harmful impact on our ecosystems and health. Therefore, the consortium welcomes the news that the UN Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee will reconvene in Geneva from 5 to 14 August 2025 for a critical round of negotiations on a Global Plastics Treaty, after failing to reach an agreement last December in Busan.

This treaty would be a crucial step forward in preventing the widespread contamination of micro- and nanoplastics that now permeate our waters, soils and agri-food chains. Achieving a strong agreement in Geneva would be a landmark victory in safeguarding both environmental and human health.

"Biosolids, compost, organic fertilizers, and wastewater are a major source of microplastics"

A discussion with Demetres Briassoulis (AUA), leader for WP1 (Properties & sources of plastics) - Interview by L. CHANGEUR

What are the key takeaways from this study in your area of expertise?

Agricultural plastics (APs) are potential sources of soil pollution as they release micro- and nano-plastics (MNPs), depending on their characteristics. APs designed to be used as polymer coatings for fertilisers (PCFs) and coated seeds, are often incorporated into the soil. The same happens for agricultural plastics in direct contact with soil (such as mulching films).

However, the major source of soil pollution is represented by MNPs entering soil indirectly through biosolids, compost, wastewater used for irrigation, wind, runoff, and the mismanagement of all APs

at their end-of-life. In this case, the amount of microplastics released differs depending on the degradation behaviour of each product.

What measures could be implemented to address this issue on the ground, at the farm level?

Farmers play a key role in mitigating soil pollution by:

- making informed choices about selection and use of APs;
- following the guidelines for the proper management and recycling of APW.

The industries are responsible to provide proper certification and correctly labelling their products.

Additionally, while biosolids, compost, organic fertilizers, and wastewater are often promoted as environmentally friendly agricultural practices, their use should be avoided unless they are strictly controlled and certified as free of micro- and nano- plastics to prevent further soil contamination.

What actions could be considered at the European level, particularly within the framework of interinstitutional negotiations on the Soil Protection Directive?

The solution to the problem of microplastic soil pollution should result from an integrated approach that includes:

- Investment in research ;
- Innovative design of products ;
- A proper use, recycle, and end-of-life management of plastics ;
- Transparent and clear certifications and labels for organic fertilisers, treated wastewater, biosolids, and biodegradable plastics.

This requires the establishment of a dedicated legislation for the proper collection and waste management at EU level, incorporating essential

infrastructure, technical specifications, and traceability throughout the entire material recovery process. Random sampling should be performed on markets to verify the respect of the rules.

What could be the next steps for the Papillons Project?

The Papillons Project outcomes have revealed several important open research issues that need to be further addressed through dedicated follow-up research project(s). For example, the biodegradability of agricultural plastics has shown different effects depending on geographical climatic and soil conditions, materials composition and certification schemes.

How might this issue raise concerns among both consumers and farmers in the future?

Communication, dissemination and training activities along with proper legislative actions and motivations at EU level, especially concerning APW mismanagement and the use of various “environmentally friendly” inputs (e.g., biosolids and wastewater).

" Monitoring of microplastic in soils would help define sustainable practices "

**A discussion with Rachel Hurley (NIVA),
leader of WP2 (Plastic behaviour and Transport) -
Interview by L. CHANGEUR**

What are the key takeaways from this study in your area of expertise?

Soil microplastic pollution has diverse origins, where no single source or release pathway is dominant across Europe. This means that we can't just look in one direction to find an easy solution: we need holistic strategies that bring together a wider range of actors. We are also only now starting to uncover what happens to these microplastics once they enter soils: there is evidence that particles move down to deeper soil layers but that a large portion remains in the upper part of the soil and is available for surface runoff processes during rainfall events - meaning that soils may also act as a pathway for pollution to other environments.

What measures could be implemented to address this issue on the ground, at the farm level?

We can likely address soil microplastic pollution by understanding the inputs, factoring in long-term ecological risks within cost-benefit analyses for implementing practices that may add microplastics to soils, and managing soils well. However, the answers to these questions are not always clear-cut. More research is needed to better

understand source dynamics and to define what sustainable practices look like within different agricultural and biogeographic regions.

What actions could be considered at the European level, particularly within the framework of interinstitutional negotiations on the Soil Protection Directive?

Monitoring of microplastic in European soils would help to identify relevant sources of pollution and define sustainable practices. Monitoring data would provide crucial insights into what might lead to high or low levels - such as different agricultural practices or local environmental conditions like the type of soil. Detecting microplastic levels in agricultural soils would also help to give an indicator of whether these soils are at risk of the negative consequences of pollution, which may impact soil health or plant productivity and, in turn, the security of quality food supplies and farm economies.

What could be the next steps for the Papillons Project?

The PAPILLONS project has made a substantial step forward in our understanding of soil plastic pollution and

its potential impacts. However, as with most research, our answers also raise new important questions. We need to continue filling these research gaps to understand how our results play out over different spatiotemporal scales, at different levels of ecological complexity, and in response to different environment variables. To do this effectively, it is also essential to continue working together with relevant actors to ensure that the research is grounded in the farm context and that potential solutions can efficiently and collaboratively emerge from the observations we make.

How might this issue raise concerns among both consumers and farmers in the future?

Soils face many present and future threats. Damaging soil ecosystems, particularly in ways that are difficult or impossible to reverse, can undermine food or nutritional security in the future. Soils that cannot sustain the same quality or quantity of crops will have grave impacts for farm economies and public health. There is an urgent need to better characterise the diverse array of threats to soils and develop meaningful solutions that don't create new problems in themselves. This is possible if consumers, farmers, scientists, and politicians work together.

“The PAPHILLONS project has made a substantial step forward in our understanding of soil plastic pollution and its potential impacts.”

- Rachel Hurley

PAPILLONS-MINAGRIS Stakeholder Forum

AGRIFOODPLAST Science-Policy Opening Session

AGENDA

Tuesday, April 8 - Morning

 Thon Hotel EU, Brussels, Belgium

9h00-10h00: Arrival of the attendees & welcome coffee

10h00-10h30: Opening session - Microplastics: red alert for European soils?

Speakers:

- Alessandra Moretti, *Member of the European Parliament (S&D, Italy)*
- Luca Nizzetto, *Senior research scientist Norwegian Institute for Water Research, Coordinator of the PAPILLONS project*
- Luc Vernet, *Secretary General of Farm Europe, WP Leader in PAPILLONS*

10.30-11.10: Roundtable n°1 – The Soil Monitoring Law: an opportunity for European soils?

- Moderator: Luc Vernet, *Secretary General of Farm Europe, WP Leader in PAPILLONS*
- Speakers:
 - Annalisa Corrado, *Member of the European Parliament (S&D, Italy)*
 - Mirco Barbero, *Team Leader of Soil Team of the Unit Land Use & Management, DG Environment, European Commission*
 - Christian Laforsch, *Professor, Chair Animal Ecology, Faculty of Biology, Chemistry and Earth Sciences, University of Bayreuth, member of PAPILLONS*
 - Edoardo Puglisi, *Professor in Agricultural Microbiology at the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, member of MINAGRIS*
 - Caroline Heinzl, *Policy Officer for Soil, European Environmental Bureau*

11h10-11h25: Coffee break

PAPILLONS-MINAGRIS Stakeholder Forum

AGRIFOODPLAST Science-Policy Opening Session

AGENDA

11h25-12h05: Roundtable n°2 - Exploring the economic, environmental and social impact of micro- and nanoplastic pollution

- Moderator: Luca Nizzetto, *Senior research scientist Norwegian Institute for Water Research, Coordinator of the PAPILLONS project*
- Speakers:
 - Richard Thompson, *Professor of Marine Biology at Plymouth University, creator of the term “microplastics”*
 - Elsa Vinuesa, *Comité de la Plasticulture et de l'Agroenvironnement*
 - Ms. Jackie Flannery, *Irish Rural Association*
 - Kees Van Gestel, *Professor of Ecotoxicology of Soil Ecosystems at the Free University of Amsterdam, member of PAPILLONS*

12h05-12h45: Roundtable n°3 - Which paths towards a sustainable use and management of agricultural plastics?

(organised in collaboration with the FAO)

- Moderator: Lev Neretin, *Head of Environment and Social Management Unit, Office of Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environment (OCB) at FAO*
- Speakers:
 - Werner Bosmans, *Policy Officer, DG Environment, European Commission*
 - Violette Geissen, *Professor, Wageningen University, member of MINAGRIS*
 - Natalia Rodriguez, *Land and Water Officer, FAO (TBC)*
 - Valentina Elena Tartiu, *Research Scientist, NIVA*
 - Rose Souza Richards, *Phytosanitary Affairs Manager at the International Seed Federation (ISF), and member of the International Agri-Food Network (IAFN)*
 - Pierre de Lépinau, *ADIVALOR*

12h45-13h00: Conclusion by Luca Nizzetto

"Some ecological effects occur at concentrations present in the agricultural soil today"

**A discussion with Salla Selonen (SKYE),
leader for WP 3 (Ecological effects of plastics) -
Interview by L. CHANGEUR**

What are the key takeaways from this study in your area of expertise?

- Some ecological effects of MPs occur at concentrations present in the agricultural soil today. In our researches, we studied the ecological impacts of microplastics on different soil organisms and in different scales from laboratory to field. As we used the same test materials, we were able to compare the effects between organisms and experiments. The impacts of microplastics depend on the exposed organism, some species being more sensitive than others, but also on the complexity of the experiments. In some cases, the effects were seen only in the field or at the mesocosm scale and already at concentrations environmentally relevant today. Since environmental MP concentrations are increasing rather than decreasing by time, precautionary principle should be followed to prevent plastic pollution.
- The effects can worsen after long-term exposure to MPs. In some PAPPILLONS experiments, no impacts of MPs on adult organisms were seen, but their offspring was affected when the exposure continued over two generations. This means that the impacts of MPs may be underestimated when using traditional one-generation ecotoxicological testing.
- As plastics are persistent in the environment, the exposure of organisms is continuous from generation to generation. Thus, long-term experiments spanning several generations should be exploited to assess hazards of MPs.
- The effects of MPs on soil organisms can rise from interactions between biotic and abiotic environments. MPs were found to affect soil physicochemical properties, which can be one mechanism for the effects on biota. Also interactions between organisms may be important, but more studies are needed to better understand these interactions. The role of interactions is supported by the results from the field and mesocosm studies, where some impacts were found at lower concentrations than in laboratory experiments. This highlights the need of more complex studies with interactions between the organisms and abiotic environment.

Together we are stronger. In PAPPILLONS we have truly worked together, scientists from different countries and backgrounds. We managed to gain strong and impactful data by working together. Together we are also stronger in tackling the challenges that plastics can cause. We need co-operation between scientists, industry, farmers and policy makers.

What measures could be implemented to address this issue on the ground, at the farm level?

One key element in managing plastic pollution at the farm level is a proper waste management. Mismanagement of agricultural plastic waste, such as burning or disposal for years on field sides can result in the contamination of the soil and surrounding environment with plastics. The costs of waste management should always be included in the budgeting on the farms, and alternatives for plastic use could be considered, taking into account the possible savings in the costs of waste management. Best practices, such as techniques to remove plastics with minimum tearing could be shared among farmers. Co-operation between researchers and farmers is also needed. Informing farmers on the negative impacts of plastic pollution on soil health could promote farmers to protect the soil from plastic contamination.

What actions could be considered at the European level, particularly within the framework of interinstitutional negotiations on the Soil Protection Directive?

Monitoring European soils for macro and microplastics is needed to better understand the state of the plastic contamination in agricultural soils. When monitoring data are available, measures can be implemented and targeted properly. Implementing the Extended Producer Responsibility to cover all agricultural plastics would enhance proper management of agricultural plastic waste. Also, product development can be boosted and requirements for product features can be set at the European level. Product development is needed to produce materials that don't degrade into microplastics so easily and are easy to remove without leaving plastic fragments behind. Biodegradable plastics, in turn,

should be developed to adjust the product to degrade in the particular environment and climatic conditions where the plastic is used. A European level certification system for biodegradable mulching films is needed and the biodegradation criteria should take into account the climatic conditions where the product is used.

What could be the next steps for the Papillons Project?

PAPILLONS results will be implemented by communication with policy makers, farmer associations and plastic producers. In addition, several scientific publications are still to come. Further research by PAPILLONS partners is needed e.g. to understand biodegradable plastic degradation in different environmental conditions and the role of biotic and abiotic interactions on the impacts of MPs.

How might this issue raise concerns among both consumers and farmers?

Plastic pollution is already raising concerns among consumers and farmers. In a survey for another project (MicrAgri), farmers showed worries about the impacts of plastic pollution on soil health. Livestock farmers were also worried about the ingestion of plastics by animals, since plastic residues from bale wraps are easily incorporated in the provender. Considering the finding that microplastics affects soil properties, farmers may also be concerned about the joint impact of microplastic soil pollution and ongoing climate changes which are reflected in severe droughts. For consumers, especially health risks associated with crop consumption are in the focus. Concerns are also directed to chemicals in plastics. As plastics are persistent in the environment and concentrations of macro and microplastics are likely to increase, these concerns will intensify in the future.

"There is already evidence that multiple stressors increase the risk of reduced soil ecosystem functioning"

A discussion with Velmala Sannakajsa (LUKE), leader for WP4 (production and sustainability impacts) - Interview by L. CHANGEUR

What are the key takeaways from this study in your area of expertise?

Our systematic review showed that plants are sensitive to exposure to micro- and nano-plastics, even under environmentally relevant conditions. Using polystyrene micro and nanoparticles and PAILLONS reference materials (LLDPE and starch-PBAT blend), we found that different plant species reacted differently in seedling development and plant growth: starch-PBAT blend notably reduced lettuce root length after germination and decreased barley shoot fresh weight over time. In one of our experiments, biodegradable plastic induced stronger reactions on seedlings than conventional plastic. However, the effects of both biodegradable and conventional plastics on plant health remain insufficiently studied, highlighting the need for further research to understand their impact.

Other experiments revealed significant physiological and biochemical changes in lettuce, with increased oxidative stress and activation of defence mechanisms. These alterations were more pronounced and frequent with LDPE microplastics (MPs) compared to biodegradable starch-PBAT blend MPs and were also time-dependent.

So far, I'd conclude that as the result of different studies vary. This shows the importance of studying MNP effects on crops in real environmental conditions and examining various polymers and mixtures.

What measures could be implemented to address this issue on the ground, at the farm level?

Controlled waste management is the key. A proper use of plastic at farm level would reduce both costs, and the risk of generating MNP in soil.

What actions could be considered at the European level, particularly within the framework of interinstitutional negotiations on the Soil Protection Directive?

MNP pollution in agricultural soils may affect crop growth and global food security. We are still limited in our understanding of MNP in soil and what the consequences for soil carbon and nitrogen mineralization, plant growth and yield are. However, there is already evidence that multiple stressors increase the risk of reduced soil ecosystem functioning, which might reflect to crop plants and the whole food system.

Effective monitoring of nano- and microplastics in soils is essential to assess their presence and impact. Identifying the main sources of contamination is crucial for developing targeted mitigation strategies.

What could be the next steps for the Papillons Project?

We will next focus on the analysis of the field experiment data in order to understand which plant biomarkers that are sensitive to MNP. We will also complete the analysis of plastic additives in barley grain, and transfer of ¹⁴C labelled nanoplastic particle in lettuce and barley. The next steps for research should include investigating plant responses to multiple stresses, such as drought, heat, and flooding, in the presence of nano- and microplastics. Additionally, studying the leachate from various plastic types is crucial to understanding their chemical impact on soil and plant health. Further comparative studies should continue to evaluate the effects of conventional plastics versus alternative materials, assessing their environmental consequences and potential benefits.

How might this issue raise concerns among both consumers and farmers in the future?

More studies will be published in the next years showing that MNP can move from soil to plant roots, and possibly to edible parts. I cannot foresee how this will affect consumer behaviour, but farmers should take this into account when assessing the cost and benefits of plastic use on their farm. Our project will hopefully also shed light on the possible sources of MNP in soil on a European level.

MilleVigne
IL PERIODICO DEI VITICOLTORI ITALIANI
by VIGNAIOLI PIEMONTESE

PLASTICS IN

Plastic in Vineyards and Wineries: Management, Risks, and

Millevigne is an Italian technical magazine specializing in viticulture and enology. It focuses on plastic management in the wine sector through articles, events, and in-depth discussions. From ties and shelters in vineyards to equipment components and packaging, plastic is widely used in winemaking: a series of publications has explored the advantages, characteristics, and challenges of using plastic in vineyards and wineries, aiming to enhance knowledge and awareness of the materials used by producers in their activities. At the same time, they explored the life cycle of plastic materials and highlighted exemplary cases of sustainable management and the development of alternative materials.

SOSTain Sicilia

SOSTain Sicilia is a sustainability program for Sicilian viticulture, led by the Doc Sicilia Wines Consortium and Assovini Sicilia, to certify the wine sector's sustainability. We recognize that agriculture impacts not just fields but is also represented by workers, consumers, local communities, and natural resources. The program sets ten minimum requirements for certification. Namely, Requirement 4 promotes the use of eco-friendly vineyard materials. This has encouraged our wine producers to reduce the use of plastic whenever possible, and many have replaced single-use plastic, such as that used for tying the vines, with completely biodegradable materials. These efforts earned SOSTain high marks from Intertek on behalf of the Northern Monopolies, reinforcing its success in promoting sustainability.

by Lucrezia Lamastra

VINEYARDS

Solutions

A special feature on this topic was published in issue 3/2024, accompanied by a workshop at SIMEI with industry experts. Due to the strong interest, the discussion will continue at a conference on May 7 in Castagnito (CN). Titled "Plastic in Vineyards and Wineries," the event will be curated by Alessandra Biondi Bartolini (scientific director of Millevigne) and Monica Massa (editor-in-chief of Millevigne). It will address plastic use in vineyards and wineries, microplastic pollution, and food safety, followed by a roundtable on circular economy and innovative solutions.

Picture from Azienda Agricola La Casaccia.

Azienda Agricola La Casaccia

"We are a family-run farm in Monferrato (Piedmont) with 8 hectares of vineyards, 60 olive trees, a forest, a few fruit trees, and a vegetable garden. We decided to adopt organic farming in 2001 to respect our environment, as well as for ourselves, our friends, and our customers. For us, this means paying attention to ecosystems and their balance, biodiversity, and the entire Earth ecosystem, including animals and humans, to pass on the world to our children with the same beauty and opportunities that we enjoy. In particular, we do not want to use plastics in our vineyard to avoid residues and microplastics. There are alternatives, and we have chosen to tie the vines with paper ties that have an iron core, adopt a metal spring system with hooks attached to the poles to facilitate shoot growth management, and use small cardboard clips in vineyards where adding springs was not possible. We also tested biodegradable clips, but we prefer cardboard since we can observe its natural degradation from one year to the next."

by Margherita Rava

PLASTICS IN

Microplastics in vineyard soils: First insights from plastic- intensive viticulture systems.

The research by Klaus et al. (2024) was the first investigation of microplastic abundance in vineyard soils, considering both conventional and organic vineyards in the Moselle and Saar region of Germany. The study's key findings included the high levels of microplastic in vineyard soils compared to other cropping systems, and the downslope transport of microplastics by erosion on sloped vineyards. The study clearly indicates that management and cultivation practices are significant sources of microplastic in viticulture systems. Plastic products used for protecting grapes, preventing pests or cultivating the vines (e.g., nets, pheromone traps, clips or tying material) and litter items spread with green waste for mulching are the major microplastic source after fragmentation in the soil environment. Consequently, modifications to management strategies can effectively contribute to the mitigation of microplastic pollution in viticulture.

Klaus et al. (2024), *Science of The Total Environment*, 947, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174699>, by Collin J. Weber (collin.weber@tu-darmstadt.de; Website)

VINEYARDS

Vigneti Plastic Free

The Vigneti Plastic Free project, funded through PIF calls, involves 15 wineries from Tuscany and Puglia, along with the Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering at the University of Pisa (Maurizia Seggiani & Patrizia Cinelli), to develop recyclable and biodegradable bioplastic products. The goal is to replace traditional plastics in vineyards and wine packaging, reducing environmental impact and promoting sustainability in the wine industry.

Plastic waste management in agriculture is challenging due to inadequate recycling infrastructure and the poor quality of agricultural plastics, which are often contaminated with pesticides and fertilizers. Bioplastics offer a promising alternative, especially in viticulture, where collecting and recycling traditional plastics is costly and inefficient. However, these materials remain significantly more expensive, and performance issues—such as incomplete biodegradation—have led to skepticism among farmers. Greater incentives, clearer disposal guidelines, and continued research are necessary to improve bioplastic adoption in the sector.

By Patrizia Cinelli e Maurizia Seggiani

PAPILLONS Calls for Urgent Action to Address Plastic Pollution in European Soils and Food

The AGRIFOODPLAST conference taking place on April 8,9 in Brussels constitutes an opportunity for the international research community to present critical new scientific evidence on the risks posed by plastic pollution to agriculture, soil health and food safety. This initiative is promoted by a cluster of EU-funded projects involving 40 European research institutes, coordinated by the Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA), Wageningen University, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, and Farm Europe.

The latest research results highlight indeed the widespread presence of microplastics (MPs) in European agricultural soils, with levels high enough to alter soil properties and crop quality. These findings underscore the urgent need for action to control and reduce plastic pollution in agricultural environments.

MPs are the most abundant anthropogenic foods in European agricultural soils, with worst-case concentrations reaching 0.1% by weight in the soil's top layer. These levels surpass those of other well-monitored pollutants such as heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs).

Plastic pollution—both from conventional and biodegradable plastics—affects crucial soil properties and functions, as well as plant growth and quality. Field and mesocosm studies confirm negative impacts on microbial communities, nutrient cycles, and plant physiology, even at environmentally realistic exposure levels.

Furthermore, microplastics and plastic-related chemicals can enter the food chain, with strong evidence of crop uptake, raising potential risks for food safety and human health.

Call for Policy Action

The scientific community and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (contributing to the event) have already urged policymakers, farmers, and industries to work together on incentives and stricter regulations for the safer use of both conventional and biodegradable plastics in agriculture. Plastics are increasingly used in greenhouse systems, mulching films, micro-irrigation, protective nets and many other applications, making them a very important commodity in the sector, but that can easily release pollution.

Dr. Luca Nizzetto, —Coordinator of the PAPILLONS research project, and chair of the scientific committee of AGRIFOODPLAST—stresses the urgent need for decisive action against plastic pollution to protect soil health, food safety, and human health. In these days, the EU is debating the Soil Monitoring Directive, a policy instrument designed to achieve healthy soils by 2050 and maintaining them in optimal conditions

thereafter. However, the European Parliament is the only institution that presented a series of amendments to include the monitoring of microplastic presence in soils as a requirement for Member States, whereas the original draft entirely overlooked plastic pollution. This is very worrisome considering that we are approaching the date for the last trilogue negotiations on April 8. The scientific evidence presented at AGRIFOODPLAST calls for an amendment to include plastic pollution and a swift ratification of the law.

An EU-wide policy instrument is essential to ensure quality control, and to protect the competitiveness of food producers who invest in clean and sustainable agriculture: "Soils may be considered a national matter, but the food grown on them is traded across borders," says Nizzetto. "European citizens must be assured that the food they consume, regardless of its country of origin, is grown in healthy soil, free from MNPs, plastic chemical additives, and plant stress metabolites linked to plastic exposure."

For more information, visit www.papillons-h2020.eu.

PAPILLONS' Message to Policymakers

In line with its objective to exploit its scientific results to better orient policymakers' decisions on the issue of MNPs contamination of European agricultural soil, PAPILLONS has drafted a policy brief to illustrate its main findings, remaining research gaps and policy recommendations. This paper was destined to the European institutions and was originally written to spread a clear message ahead of the last round of trilogue negotiations on the Soil Monitoring Directive. Here below is a summarised version of the brief. The sources for the exposed results can be found in PAPILLONS studies.

Main Results

1. Microplastics are the most abundant, widespread anthropogenic food of European agricultural soils
2. Microplastics affect key soil properties and functioning at field conditions and realistic exposure levels.
3. Microplastics at environmentally realistic condition affect physiology, reduce chlorophyll content, and to some extent affect growth of plants.
4. Crops and organisms uptake plastic and chemicals from soil and store them in edible parts.

Remaining Knowledge Gaps

- Understanding actual degradability (of biodegradable plastics) under different European field conditions is needed to address the dosing of soil that will prevent accumulation of

- residues exceeding effect thresholds for soil and food quality.
- EU and national research programs should further invest in the development of knowledge on plastic sources to the soil environments (from both agricultural and non-agricultural sources), the long-term fate of plastics and their chemical additives in soil, the accumulation of plastic and chemical additives in food.
- Long-term impact on soil health: while some effects on soil properties were observed in the short term, the evolution of these impacts over longer timescales and whether they could lead to irreversible soil degradation should further be observed.
- Cumulative and interactive effects: the interaction of MPs with other agricultural pollutants (e.g., pesticides, heavy metals) and their cumulative effects over multiple growing seasons require further investigation to assess

compounding risks to soil and crop health.

- Defining a “low plastic content” certification for biofertilizers: this definition could be elaborated considering the requirement that the reiterated addition of the fertilizer during the long period will not result in a measurable increase of MP level in soil.

Recommendations

- The Soil Monitoring Law shall include MPs as critical soil foods. Monitoring should take place every 5 years to provide a useful level of control.
- National and European authorities shall enact actions to monitor evolution of MP levels in soils, identify source pathways and reduce emissions. They should also invest in further research on the topic (see the Remaining Knowledge Gaps).

- The use of biodegradable plastic in agriculture should be revised and informed by a complete risk assessment and risk management scheme (including strict, traceable certification and quality control/assurance practices). No excess of biodegradable plastic residues should be reached through continuous applications in a given soil.
- The EU should create a “low plastic content” certification for biofertilizers. Restriction or ban of practices known to cause substantial addition of plastic to soil should be considered.

See you soon, PAPILLONS!

The last words from our project coordinator Luca Nizzetto, Senior Scientist at NIVA

After four years of intense and challenging work, PAPILLONS is approaching its conclusion. Thanks to the support of the European Union, the project brought together twenty research institutes and nearly one hundred scientists from ten countries. Together, we contributed to pioneering research on the sources, behaviour, and effects of micro- and nanoplastics in soil and crops.

When the project began in 2021, little was known about this issue. Most of the concerns around microplastics focused on their impact on marine environments. Since then, PAPILLONS—together with our sister project MINAGRIS and many other initiatives—has helped shift that paradigm: terrestrial environments and in particular agricultural soils are now recognized as the major recipients of microplastics. Our research confirms the widespread presence of microplastics in European agricultural soils, with concentrations that can alter soil properties and affect crop quality. We can now firmly say that microplastics are the most abundant man-made contaminants in soils with observed worst cases where the levels exceed 0.1% by weight in the topsoil—higher than many other pollutants we monitor.

Plastic pollution—whether from conventional or biodegradable plastics—affects soil structure and functions, plant growth, and overall soil health. Our field and mesocosm experiments show clear impacts on soil microbes, - nutrient cycles,

and plant physiology at concentrations that are typical of many European fields.

Plastic has become an important commodity for agricultural production and the use and mismanagement of plastic mulching films, covers, greenhouse films, bags, clips, seed coatings, or slow-release fertilizers (among other applications) can pollute soil. However, this is not the only source of microplastics. The application of contaminated biosolids as soil fertilizers is a crucial and sometimes predominant input, along with diffuse atmospheric depositions conveying microplastics from a multitude of non-agricultural sources. In short, plastic pollution in soils is a complex and growing issue that will require coordinated actions across many sectors to bring the problem under control.

Soil and human health are interlinked. Microplastics and plastic-related chemicals present in soil can enter the food chain. There is strong evidence that crops can absorb and translocate them to edible parts. Plastic pollution is building up in soil, and without action, critical thresholds could be crossed. While our core focus has been research on, one objective of PAPILLONS was to maintain engagement in policy discussions for the broader safeguard of agri system quality and safety. Collaborating with the European Commission, we contributed to shaping the international agenda on soil health. Throughout the project, we've worked closely with farmers, industry

stakeholders, and regulators across Europe to share our findings and support the development of solutions for more sustainable agriculture.

As PAPPILLONS concludes, we mark an important milestone in the progress of knowledge in this area, but our commitment toward cleaner and safer agrifood systems, continues. A European-wide policy is crucial to ensure quality standards and to protect the competitiveness of farmers investing in clean, sustainable practices.

Ultimately, protecting soil from plastic pollution is a matter of protecting our health. Nanoplastics present in food can be absorbed through the human digestive system and accumulate in organs such as the liver, kidneys, reproductive system, and the brain. A recent study published in Nature Medicine revealed traces of plastics in human brain tissue, showing the first evidence of a potential link to neurodegenerative conditions. Shockingly, the levels found in some human tissues mirror those found in the most contaminated soils we studied. We strongly urge policymakers and stakeholders to take action. The time to protect our soil, food, and health is now.

MINAGRIS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000210